

THE STATUS CURRENCY OF SPORT IN AFYONKARAHISAR, TURKEY

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study is to determine the currency of the sport in Afyonkarahisar with economic, social and cultural movements in recent years. What is the rate of the participation to amateur and professional sports? Is sports facility sufficient? Have the school sports become common? How it looks relation between branch and participation and the level of the success in clubs? The responses of these questions is important to identify what to do for the city people, who ask to catch output in the field of sport in Afyonkarahisar, spend their times with sports activities. It is needed to determine the place of Afyonkarahisar, which had a very significant role in Republic and before the Republic period, in Turkish Sports History and what to do in order to make it a better city. In last 25 years, it's discussed with the people who served as Afyonkarahisar Youth and Sport city manager, Afyonspor's old and new administers the athletes who are successful enough to play in national teams and the physical education teachers who are working in the city and the results have been noted. After the investigation, it is presented suggestions of solution and determinations by establishing the situation of sports in Afyonkarahisar.

Keywords: Afyonkarahisar, sports, prevalence of sports, currency of sports

1. Introduction

What is the prevalence of the sport in Afyonkarahisar? How do the Physical Education Teachers, who has one of the most important responsibilities about making sport more prevalent and popular, and the provincial directors of Youth and Sports in Turkey approach the prevalence of the sport, and how do they look at it?

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By specifying a route map to conduct our study in Afyonkarahisar, we will study on the adoption of the sport by the people, and obstacles to transition from the school sports to the amateur and Professional sports. The purpose of this study is to determine the prevalence of the sport in Afyonkarahisar.

1.1 Sport in Afyonkarahisar

While the sport fields wrestling, hunting, shooting and athletics were being fundamentally performed in accordance with the Afyonkarahisar Provincial Sample, Two sport clubs were established in the name of Gençler Birliği Sport Club and Kocatepe Sport Club after the foundation of Turkish Training Hall (Türk İdman Yurdu) in 1920. With the enacting of the Physical Education Law no 3530, the Physical Education Organizations was founded and the Gençler Birliği, Kocatepe, Merkez Gençlik, Doğan Spor, Toprakspor and 27 Ağustos Sport Clubs were registered officially in Afyonkarahisar.

As a result of the obligations forced by the law, the trainings have started conducting their works in the regional building and the organization is still continuing their works in the same building. In 1937, the first local football trainer course was opened in Afyon. The next year in 1938, the sport activities in the fields of Athletics, Football, shooting, boxing and wrestling were carried out in Afyonkarahisar where the youth movements started with a fresh understanding and spirit. The first officially appropriate sized football pitch in a statutory stadium today named as Atatürk Sport Facilities was built by the Governor of the Province and late Ahmet Evrendirek (1932-1966) who was the Regional Chief of the Sport Organizations by providing a 67.135 meter area. On the 1st of June 1972, the football pitch was turfed with grass and this situation has been conserved since then. In 1975, the central heating system was installed and in 1985, the audience tribune built and started to serve. The grass football pitch has 6 tracks and the athletics running track arranged in accordance with the new regulations started to provide service in 1986. Besides, near the main stadium, there are two more proportionate football pitches surrounded by wire fence and a reduced sized training pitch.

The Indoors sport facility started to be built by the SporToto Organizations in 1967 came into use in 1970 with a 2000 people capacity audience tribune. In 1967, Afyon Sport Club was founded and the team represented Afyon City in the Second Football League with the colors Purple and White. Until now, 60 sport clubs has been registered since 1938. (Afyon Provincial Governorship, 1938)

1.2 The Conditions of the Sport Facilities in Afyon

According to the information received from Afyonkarahisar Directorate of National Education, there are 26 high schools, 66 elementary schools and 19 religious vocational elementary schools. Only 9 of these schools have sport halls. These facilities have tribunes of 250 people. (Afyonkarahisar MEM, 2015).

Afyonkarahisar Sport Facilities (GHSİM 2015):

- Merkez Atatürk Sport Hall, 2000 people

- Sports Complex, 500 people
 - Sports Complex, 1000 people
 - Central Atatürk Stadium, 10.000 people
 - Central Football Pitches No 1,2,3
 - Sports Complex 8 football pitches
 - Stadium, 15.000 people
 - 2 Sports Complexes, 1 Youth center, 1 Sportsman Training Center
 - 1 swimming pool, 1 portable swimming pool
 - 1 semi Olympic swimming pool sports complex 500 people
 - 4 Tennis Courts, 1 Indoor Tennis Court, 1 Athletics Gymnasium
- In the School of Physical Education and Sports:
- 2 Indoor Sports Halls, 1 Gymnastics Hall, 1 aerobics Hall
 - 1 Outdoor Football Pitch, 2 Tennis Courts

In Afyonkarahisar City, there are 16 Public Sports Halls having 7.500 person capacity in total in service of the Directorate of the National Education (MEM), Provincial Directorate of the Youth and Sports (GHSİM) and the University. In addition, Afyonkarahisar has the City Stadium with the capacity of 25.000 people. It also has 3 swimming pools: one of them is an Olympic swimming pool and one is a portable swimming pool. Furthermore, there are 2 athletics fields, 15 football pitches and seven tennis courts. In Afyonkarahisar, where has a population of 283.120, the capacity of the public sports facilities is 42.500 people. In other words, the number of the athletes per sports hall is 6600. According to these calculations done by considering only the central population in Afyonkarahisar, the sports facilities in the city are insufficient. There are 34251 licensed athletes doing sport actively. The athletes' number per sports facility is calculated as 1240 according to these findings. (Afyonkarahisar GHSİM, 2015).

2. Method

In this part, the model, method, study group, data collection and the information about the analysis and the results used in the research are presented.

In this study, the descriptive survey model aiming the facts to be described objectively as they are has been used. The Survey Model is the research approach which aims to describe a condition that existed in the past or still exists as it is. (Karasar, 2012) To determine these features, the interview technique was applied by getting appointments in advance. The visual and aural information received from the interviews transferred into digital media as video, photograph and voice files; besides, they were written down on papers.

The researcher gave information to the participants about the research and stated that participating in the survey is based on voluntariness. The researcher had an active role in conducting the study and the process by making clear statements and explanations during the interviews made with the physical education teachers and the Provincial Directors of the Youth and Sports.

The population of this study is Afyonkarahisar Province. Besides, the sample of this study consists of the 22 physical education teachers actively in charge and three ex provincial directors of the Youth and Sports who had been in charge and still live.

In this study, the internet, related books, magazines, published documents and photographs were scanned by using the key words. The interviews have been made face to face with the physical education teachers and recorded via cameras by getting appointments in advance. After that, the people who worked as the directors of the youth and sports and still alive were reached; then, the face to face interviews were made in the same technique by recording the videos of the process via cameras. The data received have been transferred into digital media.

The interviews recorded as videos were also written down properly and a descriptive analysis has been performed.

3. Findings

Table 1: The problems the physical education and sports teachers working in Afyonkarahisar come across

Kişi	My school isn't adequate for sports	Facilities are weak	I can't benefit from the facilities	The school authorities don't support	MEM don't support	GHSIM don't support	Private schools are more advantageous	Teog, lys, ygs exams affect sporting activities
1. Interview	x	X	x	x	x	x	x	----
2. Interview	x	----	x	x	x	x	----	x
3. Interview	x	----	x	x	x	x	----	x
4. Interview	x	----	x	x	x	x	----	x
5. Interview	----	x	x	x	x	x	----	x
6. Interview	----	----	----	----	----	----	----	x
7. Interview	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
8. Interview	x	----	x	x	x	x	x	x
9. Interview	----	----	x	x	x	x	x	x
10. Interview	----	----	x	----	----	----	x	x
11. Interview	x	x	x	----	----	x	x	x
12. Interview	----	----	x	x	x	x	x	x
13. Interview	x	----	x	x	x	----	x	x
14. Interview	----	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
15. Interview	----	----	----	----	x	----	----	----
16. Interview	x	x	x	----	x	x	x	x
17. Interview	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
18. Interview	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
19. Interview	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
20. Interview	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
21. Interview	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
22. Interview	----	----	x	x	x	x	x	----

When the table 1 is examined, it is seen that there are 22 teachers in total answering the questions. 14 teachers say that their schools aren't convenient for doing sports, 11 teachers say that the facilities in Afyonkarahisar is insufficient; 20 teachers say that they cannot benefit from these existing facilities; 17 teachers say that the school administration do not support the sport activities; 19 teachers say that the Directorate of the National Education doesn't support the sport activities; 18 teachers say that the directorate of the Youth Services and the Sports doesn't support the sport activities, 16

teachers say that the private schools are more advantageous than the public schools and 19 teachers say that the examinations such as TEOG, LYS, YGS affects the attendance in the sport activities negatively.

Table 3: School Attendance Table

		Branches	Junior Men	Junior Women	Juvenile Men	Juvenile Women	Young Men	Young Women	Total
2014-2015 The Number of The School Athletes	Football		56	28	35	21	168	56	364
	Handball		60	48	48	36	96	48	336
	Volleyball		30	80	78	340	204	384	1116
	Basketball		76	92	80	70	130	38	486
	Football		432	0	582	40	368	0	1422
	Total		654	248	823	507	966	526	3724
		Branches	Junior Males	Junior Females	Juvenile Males	Juvenile Females	Young Males	Young Females	Total
2014-2015 The Number Of The Individual Sports Athletes	Athletics		30	20	40	26	25	15	156
	Badminton		22	20	18	20	15	17	92
	Fencing		15	12	20	16	14	16	93
	Wrestling		0	0	24	9	17	4	54
	Folk Dance		25	30	30	40	20	20	165
	Judo		0	0	15	10	20	10	55
	Karate		0	0	12	8	18	12	50
	Cross Running		0	0	25	20	20	16	81
	Table Tennis		15	12	20	16	24	22	109
	Chess		20	24	30	28	25	22	149
	Tae kwon do		0	0	26	19	28	14	87
	Tennis		16	14	18	22	15	20	105
	Total		143	132	278	234	241	188	1196

When the Table 3 is examined, the numbers of the athletes doing individual and team sports at schools can be seen. Whereas the most interested and performed sport is Football as team sports with 1422 athletes, Handball is the least interested branch with 336 athletes. In addition, Folk dances as an individual sport is the most interested and performed with 165 performers, while Karate is the least interested individual sport with 50 athletes.

Table 5: The number of the Amateur Sports Clubs Federations and the licensed Athletes in Afyonkarahisar

Sport Field	Women	Men	Total
Marksmanship and Hunting	0	27	27
Athletics	412	982	1.394
Badminton	287	287	574
Basketball	810	2490	3.300
Handicapped	1	4	5
Baseball and Softball	4	5	9
Billiards	3	167	170
Cycling	44	317	361
Bocce, Bowling and Dart	1	11	12
Boxing	19	254	273
Bridge	2	75	77
Gymnastics	310	174	484
Mountaineering	30	118	148
Dance	24	25	49
Fencing	211	278	489
Traditional	0	43	43

Wrestling	77	552	629
Folk Dances	1267	620	1.887
Visually and Hearing Impaired	5	79	84
Handball	275	1051	1326
Sport for everyone	1266	1910	3176
Scout craft	273	468	741
Judo and Kurash	230	278	508
Karate	505	1233	1.738
Skiing	0	10	10
Kick boxing	63	348	411
Table Tennis	527	1074	1601
Muay-Thai	87	578	665
Archery	48	100	148
Auto Sports	0	9	9
Special Athletics	28	58	86
Chess	2079	4356	6.422
Tae kwon-Do	598	1398	1.996
Tennis	83	79	162
Volleyball	1918	2482	4.400
Bodybuilding Fitness	26	228	254
Wu shu	45	246	291
Swimming	79	108	187
Orienteering Federation	1	12	13
Developing Sports Fed	0	72	72
Rugby	4	5	9
Total	11636	22594	34230

When the Table 5 is examined, the sport which has the most performers is chess having 2079 women and 4356 male athletes which make 6422 in total. The least attendant number is in horse riding with 1 athlete. Moreover, there are 4 male sportsmen and 1 sportswoman in the physically disabled sport branches. It is observed that 11636 female athletes and 22595 male athletes, 34230 athletes in total, are actively doing sport.

4. Results and Discussion

In our study titled as “The status of the currency of the sport in Afyonkarahisar, Turkey”, it is seen that the achievement status related to the sport in Afyonkarahisar province isn’t consistent and continual. The success in sports is limited with only individuals.

It is observed that the school authorities don’t support the physical education teachers efficiently in terms of the attendance of the students to the school sports, which they think the physical education lessons are unnecessary, the academic achievement level is only measured with the theoretical examinations; consequently, the sports culture hasn’t been developed properly.

It is also seen that the Provincial Directorate of the Sports and the Youth Service can’t provide efficient support and opportunities for the towns and the subprovinces. As a result of the interviews that have been made, it is detected that there isn’t any

sufficient coordination between the GHSIM (Provincial Directorate of the Youth Services and Sports) and the MEM (Provincial Directorate of the National Education). In addition, that GHSIM and MEM don't provide the sufficient support and opportunities for the physical education teachers who are the biggest supporters of the sport. That the physical conditions of the schools aren't suitable and sufficient for doing sport has caused that the physical education classes and lessons aren't efficient and thus, there aren't adequate achievements in sports.

As the sport facilities, Afyonkarahisar has 16 Sport Halls with the capacity of 7500 people in the service of the University, The Directorate of the Youth Services and the Sports, the Directorate of the National Education. Additionally, there are 2 stadiums with the capacity of 25.000 people in total. There are 3 swimming pools (one is Olympic and the other is a portable swimming pool), 2 athletics fields, 15 football pitches, and 7 tennis courts in Afyonkarahisar. However, There are 34251 athletes per one sport hall in total who do sport actively or have sports licenses in Afyonkarahisar; moreover, there are 1240 sportsmen/sportswomen per one sports facility. According to this data reached, it can be said and it is observed that there aren't sufficient sports structuring and, particularly, the licensed athletes can only benefit from the facilities during the matches and contests. Apart from the competitions, they can't fully benefit from the facilities in terms of training and practices.

Also, Afyonkarahisar, where has 17 sub-provinces, is at the 11th place in having the most sub-provinces. Therefore, it can be said that it has many sub-provinces. When the Metropolises are excluded, Afyonkarahisar is the 3rd city having the most sub-provinces. Although having many sub-provinces should be an advantage, besides being unable to use this advantage, Afyonkarahisar cannot give efficient service to the athletes and the sub-provinces comparing to the big population in the sub-provinces. The saddest thing is the local people do not give importance to this situation and there isn't any efficacious demand for more opportunities about sports in the society, despite this unsatisfying ministration.

The men's volleyball team of Afyonkarahisar promoted to the 1st league with the municipal support of the Afyonkarahisar City Hall in 2016. In addition, the men's basketball team plays at the 2nd basketball league and the Afjet-Afyonspor football team has managed to go up to the 3rd league. However, the volleyball team hasn't got any player from Afyonkarahisar province, the basketball team has only 2 players from Afyonkarahisar, and the football team has just 1 player from Afyonkarahisar city. This situation that there is only limited number of players from Afyonkarahisar in the sport clubs in the Afyonkarahisar clearly shows that the youth setup and sportsmen/women training works are not efficient given importance in the city.

Especially the interviews made with the physical education teachers and the retired Directors of the Provincial Youth and Sports (GSIM) indicate that the most important point about the currency of the sports and sports culture is the government policy. Although there are a lot of sports facilities and a great variety of opportunities in sports, these facilities and the opportunities cannot be used and benefited from efficiently due to the wrong government policies.

To provide the continuity of the achievements and success at the amateur and the school sports, it is crucial to keep the existing facilities open and available for the athletes by means of more efficient planning. The teacher expectations indicate the same, also.

The physical education teachers have high expectations from the municipalities about providing equipment, district sport fields, areas for the school sports and building sport facilities. Furthermore, they anticipate more motivational and inspirational works and encouragements.

Additionally, it is also expected by the physical education teachers that the University or the School of Physical Education and Sports should make their sport facilities available for the amateur athletes and the school sports as well as they anticipate that the new sport branches should be taught more actively

The GHSIM must carry out more inspirational works to increase the use of the sport facilities and the varieties of sports which are done. They must also work on creating a sport culture in the society by encouraging it more effectively. Similarly, the GHSIM must contribute to the city for creating a sport atmosphere by hosting the sports organizations such as the national and regional competitions or the matches between the clubs and the interscholastic matches.

Instead of organizing the school sport competitions perfunctorily and carelessly, the GHSIM must plan the organizations more carefully which aim to create a sport culture in the society by means of more enjoyable contests which entertain both the athletes and the spectators. On the other hand, the physical education teachers are also uncomfortable with the frequent planning changes and cancellations of the contests, because they cannot watch the previous/next match.

Last but not least; the organizers, associations, directorates, physical education teachers must work cooperatively to provide more efficient opportunities, equipment, facilities and communications. In this sense, the experiences and the thoughts of the old directors of the GHSIM should be considered and taken into account to make the sport organizations better, rather than discarding their fund of knowledge and ignoring them.

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